

Project INNOHYPPY: Innovative catalyst and its regeneration for clean hydrogen production via methane pyrolysis

WP2 Deliverable D.2.2.

Report on FeNi formation on γ -Al₂O₃ support by magnetron sputtering

Introduction

This deliverable report summarizes the development and validation of FeNi catalyst formation on γ -Al₂O₃ support by magnetron sputtering within WP2 of the INNOHYPPY project. The work focused on preparing Fe-based catalytic layers modified with Ni nanoclusters on γ -Al₂O₃ powder supports for application in catalytic methane pyrolysis, where methane is decomposed into hydrogen and solid carbon without direct CO₂ formation in the main reaction.

The catalyst concept combines Fe as the main active phase with a small amount of Ni introduced in the form of discontinuous nanoclusters. Fe was selected as a non-critical and comparatively abundant catalytic material, while Ni nanoclusters were introduced to support methane activation and improve process initiation. γ -Al₂O₃ was used as a high-surface-area support to disperse the active metallic components and provide thermal and structural stability.

Two related synthesis routes were assessed. First, the feasibility of Fe/Ni deposition was demonstrated on laboratory-produced γ -Al₂O₃ using the magnetron sputtering chamber with lower reachable vacuum. Second, the process was transferred to a Kurt J. Lesker PVD-75 system and applied to commercial, industrial γ -Al₂O₃ powder in order to increase process stability, improve the base vacuum, and reduce the overall synthesis time.

Methodology

The catalyst synthesis work was performed by physical vapour deposition using magnetron sputtering. The general configuration consisted of two magnetrons, Fe and Ni targets, an argon working atmosphere, and a rotatable sample holder carrying a Petri dish with γ -Al₂O₃ powder. The powder was spread as uniformly as possible in a thin layer to expose the particle surface to the sputtered flux.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the magnetron sputtering configuration used for Fe and Ni deposition on γ -Al₂O₃ powder: 1 - vacuum chamber, 2 - magnetrons, 3 - Fe target, 4 - Ni target, 5 - power supplies, 6 - Ar gas, 7 - gas inlet (MFC), 8 - vacuum gauge, 9 - Ar plasma, 10 - γ -Al₂O₃ powder, 11 - rotating holder.

In the initial system, Fe deposition was carried out at $I_{\text{Fe}} = 0.8$ A and $U_{\text{Fe}} = 480 \pm 20$ V, while Ni nanocluster formation used $I_{\text{Ni}} = 0.5$ A and $U_{\text{Ni}} = 450 \pm 20$ V. The target-to-sample distance was 5 cm. Before deposition, the vacuum chamber was evacuated using rotary and diffusion pumps to an initial pressure of approximately 4×10^{-3} mbar. Ar was then introduced as the working gas and the process pressure was maintained at approximately 6×10^{-2} mbar. Fe deposition time was varied between 1 and 5 min, while Ni deposition was limited to 50 s to promote discontinuous nanocluster formation rather than a continuous Ni layer.

The formation procedure included repeated powder mixing to improve coating homogeneity. First, Fe was deposited onto the $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder. The powder was then removed from the chamber, manually mixed, and returned for second Fe deposition step. After Fe coating, the powder was moved below the Ni cathode and exposed to short Ni sputtering. A second mixing and Ni deposition step was then applied to improve the distribution of Ni nanoclusters on the powder particles.

At the beginning of the project, catalyst formation was performed in a standard two-magnetron vacuum chamber equipped with rotary and diffusion pumps. The process was later transferred to the Kurt J. Lesker PVD-75 system, which uses rotary and cryogenic pumping. This transfer was beneficial because it shortened the overall synthesis process and enabled a substantially improved base vacuum level. It was also concluded that thinner Fe coatings should be deposited.

Parameter	Initial chamber / laboratory $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$	PVD-75 / commercial $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$
Support	Laboratory-produced $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$	Commercial $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder (Testbourne, 99.99%, 130 ± 20 m ² /g)
Base pressure	4×10^{-3} mbar	$\leq 5 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar
Working gas pressure	6×10^{-2} mbar Ar	6×10^{-3} mbar Ar
Fe deposition	0.8 A; 480 ± 20 V; 1, 3 or 5 min	0.5 A; ~ 380 V; 2 min 30 s, 5 min or 7 min 30 s
Approximate Fe thickness	~ 200 , ~ 500 and ~ 750 nm	~ 100 , ~ 200 and ~ 300 nm
Ni deposition	0.5 A; 450 ± 20 V; 50 s	0.3 A; ~ 360 V; 18 s
Deposition strategy	Two Fe deposition steps and two Ni deposition steps with powder mixing	Two Fe deposition steps and two Ni deposition steps with powder mixing

Process optimization on quartz substrates

Before coating $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powders, preliminary experiments were performed on flat quartz substrates to select suitable sputtering parameters and to understand the growth behaviour of Fe and Ni. The main objective was to form a continuous Fe coating that could act as the principal catalytic phase during methane pyrolysis, followed by the formation of discrete Ni nanoclusters on top of Fe. The deposition-rate experiments showed that, at approximately 450 V discharge voltage, 0.5 A current, and a 5 cm target-to-substrate distance, the average Fe deposition rate was close to 3 nm/s. Based on this result, the deposition parameters were fixed and the Fe deposition time varied in the subsequent catalyst series. Fe deposition durations of 1, 3 and 5 min were selected to evaluate the influence of Fe amount on catalyst properties.

Figure 2. XRD pattern of an Fe coating formed on a quartz substrate after 3 min of sputtering. The diffraction peaks confirm the formation of a crystalline Fe structure

The preliminary quartz experiments confirmed the working assumption that very short sputtering times produce isolated islands before a continuous film is formed. This behaviour was used for Ni deposition: Ni sputtering was intentionally limited to short times so that Ni would be present as separated nanoclusters rather than as a continuous layer covering the Fe phase.

Figure 3. Schematic concept of Ni nanocluster formation on an Fe coating and elemental maps of the deposited Fe/Ni structure on quartz. Fe is distributed across the coating, while Ni appears as isolated structures, supporting the nanocluster-formation approach

Analysis

Best results were achieved as the synthesis was transferred to the Kurt J. Lesker PVD-75 system and applied to commercial γ -Al₂O₃ powder. This stage focused on evaluating the influence of Fe amount on the structure and surface composition of Fe-Ni/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalysts. High-purity Fe and Ni targets (99.99%) were used together with commercial γ -Al₂O₃ powder having a purity of 99.99% and a specific surface area of 130 ± 20 m²/g.

The XRD analysis showed that the main crystalline phase was cubic Fd/3m γ -Al₂O₃. A small contribution from monoclinic A2/m θ -Al₂O₃ was also observed, most likely related to incomplete phase transformation or temperature fluctuations during industrial powder production. Fe-related peaks were again expected near 45° and 65° 2 θ and were most clearly expressed for the Fe(300 nm)Ni sample, where the Fe layer was the thickest.

Figure 4. XRD patterns of Fe coatings with Ni nanoclusters deposited on commercial $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder using the PVD-75 system at three different Fe coating thicknesses

EDS mapping confirmed successful deposition of the metallic components on the particle surfaces. Fe was distributed over the $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ particles without pronounced agglomeration or surface inhomogeneity. As the Fe deposition time increased and the Fe coating thickness increased from approximately 100 to 300 nm, the Fe signal intensity increased. Ni distribution was more fragmented than Fe, which is consistent with the much shorter Ni sputtering time and the intended formation of isolated Ni nanoclusters.

Figure 5. EDS elemental maps of Fe, Ni, Al and O for Fe/Ni catalysts on commercial $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ support with different Fe coating thicknesses.

XPS confirmed that O and Al were the dominant surface elements, reflecting the $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ support. Fe concentration increased from 5.2 at.% for Fe(100 nm)Ni to 6.6 at.% for Fe(300 nm)Ni, confirming that increasing deposition time increased the Fe amount at the surface. The Ni concentration remained nearly constant at approximately 0.4-0.5 at.% for all Fe/Ni samples, which agrees with the use of identical and short Ni sputtering conditions. Carbon was detected at 6.5-10.3 at.% and is attributed to adsorbed carbon-containing surface species formed during exposure to ambient conditions before XPS analysis.

The Fe chemical-state analysis showed the presence of both metallic Fe^0 and oxidized Fe^{3+} assigned to Fe_2O_3 , with an approximate $\text{Fe}^0:\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ratio of 1:7. Since Fe oxide peaks were not clearly observed by XRD, the oxidized phase is considered to be mainly localized in the surface layer. This confirms the expected difference between bulk-sensitive XRD and surface-sensitive XPS analyses and indicates that the catalyst surface oxidizes after synthesis or during contact with air.

Relevance for methane pyrolysis catalyst development

The developed sputtering approach produced Fe-Ni/ $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts that could be transferred to methane pyrolysis testing. In later methane-pyrolysis experiments within the project, FeNi catalysts produced in the modified synthesis system enabled hydrogen-rich gas mixtures. The

best low-temperature performance was obtained at 700 °C for Ni-containing catalysts, demonstrating that efficient catalytic activity could be achieved at comparatively lower reaction temperature. The modified catalyst synthesis system was ultimately associated with methane pyrolysis efficiency up to 82% at 700 °C.

The catalyst series also showed that Fe amount is an important synthesis parameter. Increasing Fe amount generally increased the active Fe signal and influenced the final catalytic response, while short Ni deposition produced a nearly constant, low Ni surface concentration intended to act as a nanocluster-type promoter. The ability to control Fe loading while maintaining discrete Ni modification is therefore a key outcome of the D.2.2 work.

Conclusions

- Magnetron sputtering was successfully developed and validated as a method for forming Fe-Ni catalytic structures on γ -Al₂O₃ powder support.
- On laboratory-produced γ -Al₂O₃, Fe and Ni were detected on the powder surface by SEM/EDS and XPS. Increasing Fe deposition time increased the Fe surface concentration, while Ni remained present as a lower-concentration promoter.
- XRD patterns of coated γ -Al₂O₃ powders were dominated by the support. Fe-related reflections became more visible at higher Fe loading, while Ni reflections were not resolved because of the low Ni amount and peak overlap.
- Surface-sensitive XPS showed oxidation of the Fe-containing surface layer, mainly to Fe₂O₃, while XRD indicated that metallic Fe could remain in deeper crystalline layers.
- Transfer to the PVD-75 system improved the synthesis route by providing a better base vacuum and a faster, more stable deposition process. On commercial γ -Al₂O₃, Fe loading could be tuned between approximately 100, 200 and 300 nm while maintaining a nearly constant Ni surface content of about 0.4-0.5 at.%.

Funding

The project has received financial support from the Research Council of Lithuania agreement No. S-M-ERANET-23-1.